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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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USING CONCEPT CHECKING QUESTIONS TO IMPROVE VOCABULARY RETENTION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article examines the role of Concept Checking Questions (CCQs) in improving vocabulary retention among English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners in Uzbekistan. Due to globalization and educational reforms, English language learning has become increasingly important, yet many learners struggle to retain and appropriately use new vocabulary, especially when it is taught through translation-based methods. CCQs are introduced as an effective instructional technique that helps learners develop a deeper understanding of word meaning through simple, focused questions. Unlike traditional comprehension questions, CCQs are designed to check learners' conceptual understanding of vocabulary items and promote active cognitive processing. The study draws on relevant literature to highlight the theoretical basis of CCQs within interaction-based language teaching and meaningful learning approaches. Findings suggest that CCQs enhance vocabulary retention by increasing learner engagement, clarifying meaning, and reducing misunderstandings in classroom practice. The article concludes that integrating CCQs into vocabulary instruction can significantly improve lexical learning and communicative competence in Uzbek EFL classrooms.

Key words: concept checking questions, vocabulary retention, interaction, proficiency.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rganuvchilar (EFL) orasida lug'at boyligini eslab qolishni yaxshilashda Concept Checking Questions (CCQs) ning o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Globallashuv va ta'lim sohasidagi islohotlar natijasida ingliz tilini o'rganish tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etayotgan bo'lsa-da, ko'plab o'quvchilar, ayniqsa tarjimaga asoslangan usullar orqali o'rgatilgan yangi so'zlarni eslab qolish va ularni to'g'ri qo'llashda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelmoqda. CCQlar o'quvchilarga so'z ma'nosini sodda va maqsadga yo'naltirilgan savollar orqali chuqurroq anglashga yordam beruvchi samarali o'qitish texnikasi sifatida taqdim etiladi. An'anaviy tushunishni tekshirish savollaridan farqli ravishda, CCQlar o'quvchilarning lug'aviy birliklarni konseptual jihatdan tushunganligini aniqlash va faol kognitiv qayta ishlashni rag'batlantirish uchun mo'ljallangan. Tadqiqot CCQlarning nazariy asoslarini interaksiyaga asoslangan til o'qitish hamda mazmunli o'rganish yondashuvlari doirasida yorituvchi ilmiy adabiyotlarga tayanadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, CCQlar o'quvchilar faolligini oshirish, ma'noni aniqlashtirish va dars jarayonidagi tushunmovchiliklarni kamaytirish orqali lug'at boyligini eslab qolishni kuchaytiradi. Maqola xulosasida CCQlarni lug'at o'qitish jarayoniga integratsiya qilish O'zbekiston EFL sinflarida leksik o'zlashtirish va kommunikativ kompetensiyani sezilarli darajada yaxshilashi mumkinligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: concept checking questions, lug'at boyligini eslab qolish, interaksiya, til kompetensiyasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль Concept Checking Questions (CCQs) в повышении уровня запоминания лексики среди изучающих английский язык как иностранный (EFL) в Узбекистане. В условиях глобализации и образовательных реформ изучение английского языка приобретает всё большее значение, однако многие учащиеся испытывают трудности с запоминанием и правильным употреблением новой лексики, особенно если она преподаётся с использованием переводных методов обучения. CCQ рассматриваются как эффективный педагогический инструмент, помогающий учащимся глубже понять значение слов посредством простых и целенаправленных вопросов. В отличие от традиционных вопросов на проверку понимания, CCQ направлены на выявление концептуального понимания лексических единиц и стимулирование активной когнитивной обработки информации. Исследование опирается на научную литературу, раскрывающую теоретические основы CCQ в рамках интерактивного обучения языку и подходов, ориентированных на осмысленное обучение. Результаты показывают, что использование CCQ способствует лучшему запоминанию словарного запаса за счёт повышения вовлечённости учащихся, уточнения значений слов и снижения количества недопониманий в учебном процессе. В заключении подчёркивается, что интеграция CCQ в обучение лексике может существенно повысить эффективность усвоения словарного запаса и уровень коммуникативной компетенции в EFL-классах Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: concept checking questions, запоминание лексики, взаимодействие, языковая компетенция.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant developments of recent decades has been the growing process of global integration, which has influenced all sectors of society, including higher education. In Uzbekistan, the expansion of international cooperation in economic, cultural, scientific, and educational spheres has increased the demand for professionals who possess effective foreign language skills. Consequently, proficiency in English has become an essential component of higher education, enabling students to meet both communicative and professional requirements in an increasingly interconnected world.

The ongoing internationalization of education has created a need to modernize existing curricula and teaching practices. This includes revising foreign language programs, developing innovative courses that complement traditional instruction, and implementing active learning methodologies that enhance educational effectiveness. Such reforms are particularly important in higher education institutions, where the objective is not only to provide theoretical knowledge but also to develop practical competencies relevant to contemporary professional environments.

Therefore, the expectations placed upon graduates of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan continue to rise. These requirements are justified by the need to prepare competitive specialists who can successfully participate in both national and international labor markets (Rahimov, 2024).

Building on the growing importance of English language proficiency in Uzbekistan's higher education system, vocabulary knowledge represents one of the most fundamental components of successful language learning. As globalization and international cooperation continue to increase the demand for effective communication skills, learners must develop a sufficient lexical repertoire to participate successfully in academic and professional contexts. According to Schmitt (2000), lexical knowledge forms the core of communicative competence and serves as a crucial foundation for second language acquisition. Similarly, Nation (2001) highlights the reciprocal relationship between vocabulary knowledge and language use, arguing that vocabulary development facilitates communication, while active language use further expands learners' lexical resources.

The significance of vocabulary acquisition extends beyond classroom learning and directly influences learners' ability to function effectively in real-world situations. Research has consistently demonstrated that vocabulary knowledge is a key predictor of success in second language learning and plays a central role in the production and comprehension of both spoken and written discourse (Laufer & Nation, 1999). In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) settings, vocabulary serves as the foundation upon which the four language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—are developed. Furthermore, they emphasize that an adequate vocabulary is indispensable for meaningful communication, as learners cannot effectively utilize grammatical structures or language functions without sufficient lexical knowledge. Therefore, as Uzbekistan seeks to prepare globally competitive graduates, fostering vocabulary development should remain a central objective of English language education, enabling learners to access information, engage in professional communication, and succeed in increasingly internationalized academic and workplace environments.

However, second language learners often experience difficulties when learning and retaining new vocabulary, particularly during the early stages of language acquisition. To address this challenge, researchers have proposed a variety of strategies, methods, and techniques aimed at facilitating vocabulary learning and retention. One such widely used classroom technique is the use of Concept Checking Questions (CCQs).

Concept Checking Questions (CCQs) are instructional questions designed to verify whether learners have accurately understood the meaning of newly introduced vocabulary items or grammatical structures. Unlike traditional comprehension questions used in reading or listening activities, CCQs focus specifically on assessing learners' understanding of lexical and grammatical concepts. Their primary purpose is not to evaluate comprehension of a text or audio material but to facilitate interaction between teachers and students in order to ensure that the target language point has been clearly explained and effectively understood. Furthermore, CCQs can be employed in a variety of teaching contexts to assess learners' understanding of language functions, vocabulary, grammatical structures, and other linguistic concepts.

In many English language classrooms in Uzbekistan, vocabulary is predominantly taught through direct translation into the learners' first language. While this approach may help students recognize the basic meaning of a lexical item, it does not always ensure a deeper understanding of its usage, connotations, and contextual meaning. Consequently, learners often know the Uzbek equivalent of a word but experience difficulties when attempting to use it appropriately in authentic communicative situations. To address this challenge, Concept Checking Questions can be employed as an effective pedagogical tool. By encouraging learners to analyze and verify their understanding of a target word through guided questions, CCQs promote deeper cognitive processing and meaningful engagement with vocabulary, which can ultimately contribute to better retention and more accurate language use in real-life contexts (Thornbury, 2002).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous researchers have investigated the role of CCQs in English language teaching. For example, Workman (2006) proposed several principles for the effective use of Concept Checking Questions, including careful preparation, the use of clear and concise questions, the incorporation of varied question types, and attention to the vocabulary used in the questions themselves. The application of CCQs is closely connected with major theories and approaches in second language acquisition, particularly the Interaction Hypothesis, Comprehensible Input, Comprehensible Output, and the Negotiation of Meaning. These theoretical perspectives suggest that meaningful interaction plays a crucial role in language development. In support of this view, the author argued that learners' language proficiency is enhanced through face-to-face communication and interactive exchanges. Within this framework, display and referential CCQs provide teachers with valuable opportunities to assess learners' understanding of linguistic input while simultaneously encouraging active participation. Furthermore, it has been noted that the strategic use of questioning techniques increases students' speaking opportunities and classroom interaction, which in turn contributes to the production of richer and more accurate language output. Consequently, CCQs serve not only as an assessment tool but also as an effective pedagogical strategy for promoting learner engagement, interaction, and language development in the classroom.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research methodology based on a literature review and theoretical analysis. Relevant scientific sources related to vocabulary acquisition, Concept Checking Questions (CCQs), and English language teaching were analyzed to examine the role of CCQs in improving vocabulary retention. The study draws on previous research and pedagogical literature to identify the theoretical foundations, benefits, and practical applications of CCQs in EFL classrooms. The collected information was analyzed through descriptive and comparative methods to evaluate the effectiveness of CCQs in enhancing learners' vocabulary retention and communicative competence.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To illustrate how Concept Checking Questions can be applied in vocabulary instruction, the following examples demonstrate the use of CCQs for checking learners' understanding of newly introduced lexical items.

Target word: borrow

1. Do you take something or give something?
2. Must you return it later?
3. Is it yours?

Likewise, when teaching the adjective generous, the teacher may ask:

1. Does a generous person like sharing things with others?
2. Do they keep everything for themselves?
3. Do people usually feel happy with a generous person?

In addition to providing effective concept checking, CCQs should be designed according to several pedagogical principles. Liu (2025) emphasizes that CCQs should be simple, clear, and easy to understand. Teachers should avoid unnecessarily complex questions so that EFL learners can respond more efficiently and demonstrate their understanding without confusion. In the context of concept checking, yes/no questions are generally considered more effective than complex WH-questions (e.g., what, when, where, and who), as they enable teachers to assess learners' comprehension more efficiently and reduce the likelihood of misunderstanding during classroom interaction. Consequently, carefully designed CCQs can provide immediate feedback on learners' understanding while simultaneously supporting vocabulary retention and meaningful language use.

CONCLUSION

As English language proficiency continues to gain importance in Uzbekistan, effective vocabulary instruction has become a crucial component of successful language learning. Although many learners are able to recognize the translated meaning of new words, they often struggle to use them appropriately in authentic communicative situations. Concept Checking Questions offer a practical solution to this challenge by encour-

aging deeper processing of lexical meaning and promoting active learner engagement. The literature reviewed in this article suggests that CCQs contribute not only to the assessment of learners' understanding but also to vocabulary retention, classroom interaction, and language development. Therefore, English language teachers in Uzbekistan are encouraged to integrate well-designed CCQs into their vocabulary instruction in order to improve learners' comprehension, retention, and communicative competence.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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